

New Continuous Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites: An analysis of Interfacial Adhesion from the micro scale to the macro scale

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ABSTRACT

Acrylic matrix/fiber interfaces were investigated by considering microcomposites as models of fiber-based composites. The study was conducted considering various types of sized glass and carbon fibers. On one hand, the surface tension and dynamic contact angle measurements were used to quantify the wettability of the fibers by the acrylic matrices, i.e. as latexes. On the other hand, the debonding of acrylic droplets processed on fibers highlighted the influence of fiber sizing and of polymer matrix grafting on the interfacial shear stress (IFSS). Wettability analyses combined to practical adhesion measurements enabled a better understanding of interphase formation phenomena in acrylic thermoplastic-based composites. Relationships between the quantitative analyses obtained from microcomposites and macroscopic mechanical behavior of structural (multi-fiber) composites are also discussed. The analyses of interfaces/phases at different scales demonstrate the importance of a multi-scale approach to tailor the final properties of composite parts.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Industrial context

Fiber-reinforced Thermoset-based (TS) composites are widely used in aerospace and defence applications for which high mechanical performances are required. These composites enable major weight loss of structural parts usually made of metallic alloys. However, these materials and their processing technologies do not fit the requirements of mass production sectors such as automotive, sports and leisure. According to these new needs and environmental issues, thermoplastic-based (TP) composites appear as relevant alternatives thanks to their easier processability and better ability to be recycled[1]. Thus, recent efforts have been made to improve fiber impregnation process and to reduce process cycles in order to offer highly competitive thermoplastic-based composites to the market.

1.2 Fiber/matrix interface/phase

The interphase of a composite material can be defined as the region where fibers and matrix are chemically and/or mechanically combined and indistinct. The influence of fiber/matrix interphase on the mechanical behavior of composite materials has been widely studied over the past decades[2–4]. Indeed, the quality of the load transfer from the matrix to the fiber, based on the structure of the fiber/matrix interphase, will determine the mechanical performances of the final part (Figure 1). According to Swain et al. [4], the “composite effect”, described as the mechanism of synergetic response of isolated components (fiber and matrix) brought together to create a material with higher performances, is the correct definition of the mechanical response of the interphase. Thus, the study of

interfacial adhesion and its related phenomena in fiber-reinforced composite materials are required for relevant design processing conditions.

Figure 1- Fiber/matrix interphase of a fiber-reinforced composite material [5]. SEM micrograph of acrylic-matrix/glass fiber composite (V=10 kV, Mag=1000x, scale bar 30µm)

1.3 Aim of study

According to the multi-scale nature of composite materials, the first step for designing structural TP-based composites was to study the interfacial adhesion between high performance fibers and a thermoplastic acrylic matrix. Acrylic-based matrices can be seen as outsider components in the composite industry and have not been widely used. Nevertheless, their mechanical (stress-strain behaviour, fracture) and optical properties are excellent. Combined to a new wet impregnation process of fibers and fabrics from an acrylic latex, the approach developed in this paper can be seen as forward-looking. The study was conducted with the aim of questioning the relationships between wettability, work of adhesion, and practical adhesion in an acrylic matrix-based composite at different scales (micro and macro). A specific focus was applied to the study of the fiber sizing and its influence on the nature of the created fiber/matrix interface.

2 QUANTIFICATION OF ADHESION AT THE MICROSCALE IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

2.1 Theories of adhesion

Adhesion is described as the set of interaction phenomena taking place at the interface between two surfaces in contact. In the specific case of adhesion between fibers and organic matrix, the existence of physico-chemical interactions including covalent bonds can be considered as the largest contribution to the interfacial adhesion. The resulting adhesion can be seen as a subtle synergy between matrix wettability of the fibers, matrix viscosity and fiber surface roughness, thus the quantitative study of interfacial adhesion in composites can be divided into two categories: “theoretical” adhesion and “practical” adhesion. “Theoretical” adhesion refers to thermodynamics of the interphase, i.e. work of adhesion generated from Van der Waals interactions and hydrogen bonds; whereas “practical” adhesion refers to the energy necessary to separate the joined components, i.e. to break the interface. From these definitions, one can consider two types of analyses to quantify adhesion between fibers and matrix. First, wettability measurements will enable a precise analysis of the surface energy of fibers, acrylic matrix and wetting coefficient of the fibers’ surface by acrylic matrix [6–8]. These experiments will allow a quantification of the work of adhesion between the wet matrix (acrylic latex) and the

fibers W_a^{LF} , and of the work of adhesion between the dried state matrix and the fibers W_a^{MF} . Secondly, the microbond test will give quantitative data on the interfacial shear strength between the fibers having different natures and sizings, and acrylic matrix[9].

2.2 Wettability measurements

Wetting is defined as the ability of a liquid to maintain contact with a solid surface, resulting from intermolecular forces (polar and dispersive forces). An abundant scientific literature concerns contact angle measurements, wettability and adhesion, starting with the works of Zisman[10], Fowkes[11], and Good[12], all based on the Young-Dupré equilibrium formula. To calculate surface energies of solids or liquids, most of the developed theories consider static conditions. The Wilhelmy method [13] was chosen to characterize the wetting by measuring advancing contact angles (Figure 2 a)). A Dataphysics tensiometer (recording electro-microbalance) was used. Four fibers of ~1cm long were glued to the measuring head. The advancing speed during measurement was 0.1 mm/min until final immersion of 5 mm of fibers in latex.

Figure 2 – a) Configuration of advancing contact angle. b) Equilibrium of forces (gravity and wetting force) on the advancing fiber (mg =weight of single fiber, p =fiber perimeter, γ_L =surface tension of the latex, θ_a =advancing contact angle)

By gathering preliminary results with the recorded advancing contact angle data, interfacial tension γ_{SL} (S for solid and L for liquid) and wetting coefficient S (calculated from γ_S , γ_L and γ_{SL}) were determined. To evaluate the quality of the wetting of fibers by latex, the empirical Zisman criterium states that wetting is good only if $\gamma_L \leq \gamma_C$ (maximum surface tension of liquids which wet perfectly the fiber surface). To this first approach, Wu[8] added that a wettability optimum can be reached if the polarities of the two components are equal. A simple question can now be raised: does a good wetting guarantee a good level of practical adhesion? Namely, are wettability measurements and microbond test results related?

2.3 Microbond test

The microbond test is a micromechanical test derived from the widely studied pull-out test [14,15]. The geometry of the test, as shown in Figure 3 a), is straight-forward: a droplet of acrylic latex was deposited on a taut single fiber. The “droplet on fiber” system was then dried during 5 minutes at 250°C. After curing, the “matrix droplet on fiber” system was glued to a piece of paper with epoxy Araldite® glue. After one night of drying at 25°C, the samples were tested under an optical microscope and tested on a MTS 2/M testing machine with a 10 N sensor at a speed of 0.1 mm/min. The symmetrical metallic blades blocked the droplets. The interface stood until reaching a maximum debonding force, after which the droplets slide along the fiber with a corresponding friction force.

Figure 3 – a) Configuration of microbond test. b) Interfacial shear stress (τ_{av}) (F: debonding force, r_f : fiber radius, L_e : embedded length) calculation considering a constant shear stress along the embedded length

The microbond test is relatively easy to set up and can be applied to a wide range of fiber/matrix systems. The test enables a quantitative analysis of the fiber/matrix interface without considering interaction parameters related to stress fields of different fibers in multi-fiber based composites. Microscopy analyses of the specimens before and after debonding of the droplet were used to study the fracture processes. The main hypothesis established to calculate the average Interfacial Shear Stress (τ_{av}) is a constant stress along the embedded fiber (Figure 3 b)). This hypothesis is first approximation to gather a set of data concerning the fiber/matrix interface performances. A number of mathematical and/or physical models have been developed to improve this formula by taking into account the stress distribution along the embedded fiber, crack propagation and/or energy dissipation during debonding [16,17].

3 EXPERIMENTAL PART: MATERIALS

3.1 Acrylic Matrix

The acrylic matrixes studied in this work were processed from a latex, i.e. a concentrated aqueous emulsion of acrylic polymer. Thus, the wettability experiments were conducted by studying the wetting of glass and carbon fibers by various acrylic latex (non reactive NR and reactive R), whereas the microbond test was conducted on solid acrylic droplets (cured acrylic latex) processed on fibers. These acrylic-based emulsions have been chosen for their ability to impregnate fibers (due a low viscosity) and for the good thermomechanical properties of the resulting matrix.

3.1.1 Properties of acrylic latexes

The studied acrylic latexes are highly concentrated (50%wt solid content). The consolidation mechanism proceeding in the same way as the one from which the latex particles coalesce and pack to form a bulk transparent film (see coalescence mechanism, Figure 4) is used to make acrylic composites. This phenomenon occurs when temperature rises, driving the water to evaporate at a temperature denoted as the “Minimum Film forming Temperature” (MFT) which is higher than the glass transition temperature, T_g , as interdiffusion of polymer chains between latex particles is required. Studied acrylic latex can be divided into two categories: non reactive (NR) latex and reactive (R) latex. The non-reactive latexes will develop only physical bonds with the fibers (glass and carbon), whereas the reactive ones generate covalent bonds with the glass fiber surface.

Figure 4 – Latex film formation process [18]

3.1.2 Modified Acrylic-matrix

To enhance interfacial adhesion at the fiber/matrix interface, ARKEMA synthesized reactive acrylic latexes. The reactive acrylic latexes (R) synthesized by emulsion radical polymerization are comparable in terms of molar mass and T_g to the previously mentioned non-reactive acrylic latexes (NR). The objective is to generate covalent bonds between the glass fiber surface and/or sizing and the modified polymer chain in order to increase the interfacial adhesion, i.e. enabling acrylic matrix-based composites to display higher mechanical properties.

3.1.3 Thermomechanical properties of neat acrylic matrix

Acrylic matrix processed from acrylic latex display thermo-mechanical properties of a medium T_g-thermoplastic polymer. The main characteristics to notice in Table 1 are the T_g range and the shear stress yield value τ_y (calculated from σ_y and the Von Mises criteria).

Table 1- Thermomechanical properties of acrylic matrix processed from acrylic latex at room temperature

E (GPa)	σ_y (MPa)	τ_y (MPa)	Strain at break (%)	T _g (°C)	T _{process} (°C)
3.3	65	40	4	110-120	>200

3.2 Glass and carbon fibers

3.2.1 Glass fibers

E-Glass fibers (GF) were supplied by 3B-Fiberglass. The surfaces of two glass fibers were characterized by complementary techniques in order to analyze the sizing in terms of weight percentage, thickness, roughness and deposition state (Figure 5 and Table 2). The fibers were chosen according to the chemical nature of the sizing. AC stands for acrylic matrix designed sizing and PP stands for polypropylene matrix designed sizing.

GF	Matrix	Sizing weight %	Sizing thickness (nm)	Average diameter (μ m)
AC	Vinylester and acrylic	0.49±0.06	58	17.9
PP	Polypropylene	0.37±0.07	43	17.9

a) Figure 5: SEM micrograph of E-Glass fiber with acrylic-based sizing (AC) (V=5 kV, Mag=6000x, scale bar 10 μ m)

b) Table 2: properties of glass fiber sizings (sizing thickness was calculated from sizing weight percentage considering a continuous deposit)

The fiber sizing combines two main requirements which are adhesion (and compatibility) with the polymer matrix and the ability to be woven into fabrics [19]. The wettability quality and the resulting adhesion are strongly dependent on the chemical nature of the sizing components: film former, coupling agents, antistatic agents, etc. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) micrographs demonstrate that fibers are fully covered by the sizing layer. Darker spots correspond to regions of higher sizing concentration. The organic sizing applied to the glass fiber could react with the silanole groups on the bare fiber surface to create covalent bonds.

3.2.2 Carbon fibers

TORAYCA T700SC carbon fibers (CF) were supplied by TORAY. The surfaces of the carbon fibers were characterized by TGA, SEM, and AFM (Figure 6 and Table 3). Fibers with sizing designed for acrylic matrix and epoxy matrix, denoted as AC and E respectively, were considered.

CF	Matrix	Sizing weight %	Sizing thickness (nm)	Average diameter (μm)
AC	Vinylester and acrylic	0.7±0.1	26	8.3
E	Epoxy	0.8±0.1	30	8.3

a) Figure 6: SEM micrograph of TORAYCA T700SC Carbon fiber with acrylic sizing (AC) (V=5 kV, Mag=6000x, scale bar 10μm)

b) Table 3: Properties of carbon fiber sizings (sizing thickness was calculated from sizing weight percentage considering a continuous deposit)

(TGA analyses were performed on series of 10 dry samples of fibers of ~40mg with a TA Q500 machine. 283.15°K/min from 298.15°K to 873.15°K.)

SEM micrographs of the studied carbon fibers look very similar to those observed for glass fibers. The higher sizing concentration zones appear darker. It is important to mention that the sizing of carbon fibers is not chemically bonded to the carbon surface compared to the glass surface, the interactions between carbon fiber surface and the components of the organic sizing are only physical interactions, i.e. Van der Waals and hydrogen bonds. The sizing can be seen as a thin coating of the fiber. Carbon fibers undergo an oxidation treatment which generates polar species on the edge of the graphitic planes such as acidic groups [20–22]. Atomic Force Microscopy scans (tapping mode) of the fiber surface showed very low roughness values which lead to the fact that no mechanical interlocking phenomena can be evoked in such fiber/matrix interfaces.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Wettability

4.1.1 Preliminary results: surface tension γ_S and γ_L

Glass and carbon fiber surface tensions γ_S were measured by using a tensiometer recording advancing contact angles of fibers in water, diiodomethane and ethylene glycol. The Owens-Wendt formula was used to obtain γ_S polar and dispersive components. Acrylic latexes surface tension, γ_L , and its components were measured by using a Wilhelmy method for wet matrices, i.e. as lattices, and the sessile drop method for dried acrylic matrices, i.e. as films [23].

4.1.2 Advancing contact angle and polarity of fibers

Surface tensions of latexes and fibers values allow to calculate the interfacial tension (3) and spreading coefficient (4). These formulas are usually applied in static conditions, the advancing contact angles were considered in this work (Table 4).

$$\gamma_{SL} = \gamma_S - \gamma_L \cdot \cos\theta_a \quad (3)$$

$$S = \gamma_S - (\gamma_L + \gamma_{SL}) \quad (4)$$

Table 4 – Advancing contact angle, interfacial tension, and spreading coefficient, S, of NR acrylic latex on glass fiber and glass fibers surface energy (total and polar)

Fiber	Θ_a (°)	γ_{SL} (mN/m)	S (mN/m)	γ_s (mN/m)	γ_s^P (mN/m)
AC	58±1.7	17.6	23.7	44.7±1.6	8.0±0.7
PP	70±3.3	19.9	33.8	37.0±1.5	6.7±1.5

The higher the polar component of γ_s (i.e. the more polar the fiber) and the better the wetting is, i.e. low contact angle, low spreading coefficient, and low interfacial tension. Table 4 shows experimental values for glass fibers (PP and AC)/NR latex interfaces. The same phenomenon was observed for carbon fiber/ NR latex interfaces. The surface tension of R latex (30 mN/m) is lower than the NR latex surface tension, resulting in a better wetting of glass fibers by the R latex.

4.2 Micromechanical analysis

4.2.1 Influence of fiber sizing on Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS)

A normalization of the interfacial shear stress τ_{av} data is introduced in order to set aside the dependence to the embedded length L_e . The resulting τ_{av}/L_e value has the dimension of a volumetric force (N/m³). All experiments conducted lead to an adhesive interfacial fracture (Figure 9).

Figure 7 – Normalized Interfacial Shear Strength for glass fiber a) and carbon Fiber b) /NR acrylic matrix interfaces measured from microcomposites (AC: acrylic sizing, PP: polypropylene sizing, E: epoxy sizing)

Figure 8 stresses the fact that a compatible sizing is the key issue to get a high value of IFSS, i.e. a high level of practical adhesion for glass fiber composites as well as for carbon fiber composites. PP and E sizings which display lower levels of physical interactions with the acrylic matrix lead to low values of practical adhesion.

Figure 8 – SEM micrograph of debonded acrylic matrix microdroplet (AC/E-Glass fiber). Residual meniscus was observed (lower right side) (V=15 kV, Mag=250x, scale bar=100 μ m)

4.2.2 Micromechanical model analysis

Micromechanical models developed to describe microbond test data can be divided into two types according to the considered criteria: stress-analysis based and energy-based models. Greszczuk's model [24] which is based on the shear lag analysis ($\tau_f \ll \sigma_f$ and $\sigma_m \ll \tau_m$) was considered to be highly relevant. The latter model is based on the hypothesis that the matrix droplet doesn't display a perfect elastic behaviour and takes into account the stress distribution along the embedded fiber. The model proposes that τ_{max} , i.e. the interfacial stress for $L_e \rightarrow 0$, is the relevant parameter for interface characterization. b_i is defined as the interphase thickness undergoing shear stress during debonding. The maximum force for debonding could be calculated from (5) where L_e is the embedded length, r_f the fiber diameter, E_f the fiber's Young modulus and G_{matrix} the shear modulus of the matrix.

- Adjustable parameters: τ_{max} and b_i

$$F_{max} = \frac{\tau_{max}}{\alpha \cdot \coth(\alpha \cdot L_e)} \cdot 2\pi \cdot r_f \quad (5)$$

- Fixed parameters for all specimens:
 $G_{int} \sim G_{matrix}$ and E_f

- Measured parameters for each specimen: r_f and L_e

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{2G_{int}}{b \cdot r_f \cdot E_f}} \quad (6)$$

The two-parameter non-linear fitting was performed using Matlab software. τ_{max} is particularly relevant to our study by accounting for the limits of the fiber/matrix interfacial strength in terms of stress. The relevancy of such a model has been widely discussed[17]. The limitation of the test is related to the fracture modes which can be either mixed-modal (Mode I/II) (glass fiber based interfaces, Figure 9) or pure shear (Mode II) (carbon fiber based interfaces) and also to yielding of the acrylic matrix.

4.2.3 Enhancing adhesion in glass fiber microcomposites from acrylic matrix modification

Greszczuk model fitting enables us to discuss resulting practical adhesion from one parameter, τ_{max} . In the case of a reactive acrylic matrix (R_2), τ_{max} increases for the PP and AC sized fibers (Figure 10). Thus, enhancing adhesion in acrylic matrix composites was achieved by grafting polymer chains of latex whatever the nature of the glass fiber sizing. The set of data recorded can be compared to the interfacial shear stress determined from microcomposites (τ_{av}) for other interfaces based on acrylic and thermoset polymers (Table 5). All the experiments considered AC E-glass fiber provided by 3B-Fiberglass. The acrylic chain modification (R_2 acrylic matrix) increases the interfacial shear stress by 45% and is 10 MPa higher than the *in situ* reactive acrylic matrix from ARKEMA.

Figure 9- Greszczuk model analysis of microbond test results for GF/NR and GF/R₂

Table 5 – Interfacial Shear Strength data from different acrylic matrices on AC E-glass fiber with microbond test (MBT)

Fiber sizing	TP Matrix	τ_{av} (MPa)	Testing method
AC	NR	20	MBT
AC	R ₂	36	MBT
AC	Reactive Acrylic Elium®	27	MBT[25]
AC	Epoxy	44	MBT[25]

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Work of adhesion *versus* practical adhesion

To address the question whether theoretical adhesion and practical adhesion are related and whether the wetting level influences either one of these phenomena, we base our discussion on the harmonic work of adhesion formula (7)[8]. This formula feeds on the preliminary experimental surface energy data. The formula can be used to calculate the work of adhesion between either two solid state materials or a solid and a liquid (as shown in (7)).

$$W_a^h = 4 \cdot \left(\frac{\gamma_1^d \cdot \gamma_s^d}{\gamma_1^d + \gamma_s^d} + \frac{\gamma_1^p \cdot \gamma_s^p}{\gamma_1^p + \gamma_s^p} \right) \quad (7)$$

Comparison between the work of adhesion W_a^{MF} (dried acrylic droplet on fiber), and the interfacial shear stress τ_{av} is reported (Figure 11) for the various glass and carbon fiber/acrylic matrix interfaces. The same NR acrylic matrix was considered in all four systems. One can mention again that W_a^{MF} is calculated from the surface energies of fibers and dried matrices as films. As discussed previously, the main difference between glass fiber and carbon fiber sizings is the nature of the bonds existing between the initial fiber surface and the sizing. As expected, Figure 11 a) shows that in glass fiber/acrylic microcomposites, a high level of adhesion W_a^{MF} relates with high values of resulting adhesion (τ_{av}). In the case of carbon fiber interfaces, however, the work of adhesion and the practical adhesion cannot be directly linked. These results can be explained by the microcomposite processing method. Indeed, during the consolidation of the acrylic matrix droplet, the latex water content evaporates, which leads to a local diffusion of the carbon fiber's sizing into the latex. As a consequence, the interface is irreversibly modified, i.e. an interphase is generated and the work of adhesion which results from the characteristics of the initial components can no longer be compared to the IFSS data related to the final state of the interphase. Similar studies have been conducted on carbon/epoxy matrix systems[21,22], but the local diffusion of sizing had never been mentioned.

Figure 10 – Calculated work of adhesion (W_a^{MF}) and practical adhesion (from τ_{max}) in a) glass fiber (Sizing; PP: polypropylene, PA: polyamide, MC: multicompatible, AC: acrylic) and b) carbon fiber (O: no sizing, Sizing; E: epoxy, MC: multicompatible, TP: thermoplastic, AC: acrylic) NR acrylic matrix-based microcomposites

5.2 Micro/Macro scales

Micromechanical testing is interesting as it could be related to macro-scale experiments on the full-size composite material. Three-point bending experiment is widely used in the composite industry due to an easy set-up. However, the test is controversial due to the combination of compressive, tensile stress and shear stresses across in the sample thickness. Three-point bending experiment was performed on plain weave acrylic matrix-based glass fiber reinforced composites (50% fiber volume, 6 plies, $L/h=40$) processed by thermocompression at 250°C and 20 bar for a total cycle time of 16 min. The testing machine is an MTS 2/M, with a 10 kN sensor, the testing rate used was 5 mm/min. Table 6 shows maximum flexural stress recorded for NR (Figure 12 a)) and R (Figure 12 b)) acrylic matrixes, in comparison to the average interfacial shear stress measured by microdebonding (τ_{av}).

Table 6 - Micro and Macro-mechanical properties of acrylic matrix glass fiber composites (τ_{max} : interfacial shear stress from Greszczuk model, σ_f : maximum flexural strength on plain weave fabric composite)

AC E-Glass Fiber/Fabric	NR Acrylic Matrix	R ₁ Acrylic Matrix	R ₂ Acrylic Matrix
		Cohesive fracture	
τ_{av} (MPa)	20	>40	36
σ_f (MPa)	200	580	560

Figure 11 – SEM images of fractured surfaces of GF/Acrylic matrix composites (plain weave structure, 50% fiber volume) (a) Non reactive matrix, b) Reactive matrix (R₁)

Macro-scale mechanical experiments on composites are consistent with micro-debonding tests to account for interfacial shear stress improvement: reactive acrylic matrices enhance σ_f , even though the stress mode is not a pure shear mode. 10° off-axis tensile stress and Interlaminar Shear Stress (ILSS) experiments on UD composite materials are in progress, in order to relate unambiguously ILSS and IFSS.

6 CONCLUSION

Investigation of the interphases in glass or carbon fiber/acrylic matrix microcomposites was carried out by means of wettability measurements and microdebonding tests. On one hand, the wettability study stressed out that the polarity of the reinforcing fibers drives the latex wetting ability: the more polar the fiber, the better the wetting by acrylic latex. On the other hand, the microbond test highlights the influence of the sizing components and physical state on the interfacial shear stress value for a given acrylic matrix. The recorded data were fitted by stress-based Greszczuk model accordingly, although the fitting is strongly dependent on the considered embedded length domain. Theoretical adhesion and practical adhesion data were compared. The outcome is that any local interphase alteration during drying stage will prevent the theoretical work of adhesion of predicting the level of practical adhesion in the studied acrylic matrix microcomposites (processed from acrylic latex). Finally, the interfacial adhesion was enhanced by polymer matrix modification. The recorded microdebonding data matched macro-mechanical three-point bending results, thus confirming the importance of a multi-scale approach to tailor the resulting mechanical properties of studied acrylic composite materials.

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